

EFFECTIVE AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT OF ARDHAVABHEDAKA W.S.R MIGRAINE: SINGLE CASE REPORT

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ABSTRACT

Background: This study is performed to know about the effectiveness of Ayurvedic treatment in the patient presented with the complaints of migraine. A 13 years old, female patient consulted to the Ayurveda hospital with complaints of migraine since 1 year. **Design:** Single case report. **Materials and Methods:** This prospective case study focused on 13 years old female child diagnosed with Migraine from 1 year. She was under medication for the same and got no relief. Patient came to us with the complaints of headache for the last 1 month. The subject is admitted to the indoor patient department of *kaumarbhritya*, RGGPGAC & hospital Paprola where she was assessed every 15 days over a period of several months. The intervention included *Panchkarma* therapy alongside oral medications. Over time, the subject exhibited a progressive reduction in symptoms along with significant alleviation of

associated issues. **Results:** The patient was treated with *Shirodhara*, *Nasya*, *Akshitarpana* alongwith oral medicines which gave effective results from the starting of 1st sitting.

Conclusion: This case demonstrates the potential of *Ayurvedic* treatment in managing migraine (*Ardhavbhedaka*).

KEYWORDS: Migraine, *Ardhavbhedaka*, *Shirodhara*, *Nasya*, *Akshitarpana*.

INTRODUCTION

Migraine, the second most common cause of headache, and headache related neurological cause of disability in the world. It is characterised by unilateral, pulsatile, throbbing sensations. It is usually an episodic headache associated with certain features such as sensitivity to light, sound or movement; nausea and vomiting often accompanied by headache.^[1] It is also termed as hemicrania.^[2] Headache can be initiated or amplified by various triggers including glares, bright lights, sounds or other afferent stimulations, physical exertions, stormy weather, hormonal fluctuations during menses, lack or excess sleep and alcohol or other chemical stimulation such as with nitrates. One of the top 20 global causes of disability, according to the World Health Organisation (WHO), is migraine.^[3] Migraine can be correlated to “*Ardhavybedaka*” in *Ayurveda*. *Ardhavybedaka* is described as *Vataj* or *Vatkaphaj* in literature but *Tridoshaja Shiroroga* by *Acharya Sushruta*. Etiological factors such as consumption of dry/ununctuous substances, exposure to cold, withholding of natural urges, exhaustion, inappropriate sexual activity and exercises are quoted as the causes for Vata vitiation. Frequent intake of food before the digestion of previous meal, intake of heavy to digest food, drinking excess cold water contribute to kapha vitiation and formation of ama (a by product of impaired metabolism). Due to these etiological factors, Vata dosha alone or along with kapha affects the head and produces severe unilateral pain in the neck, eyebrows, temples, ear, eyes and forehead.^[4,5]

Epidemiology: Various epidemiologic studies from throughout the globe have shown that approximately 18% of women and 6% of men suffer from migraines.^[6]

Case report: A 13 year old female patient came to the opd with the complaints of headache from last 1 month.

History of present illness: The patient was asymptomatic, 1 month back, then the patient suddenly developed severe headache. On further enquiry patient told that pain was unilateral and chronic in nature. They also informed that pain was radiating towards bilateral periorbital region. With these above mentioned complaints, patient got admitted to IPD, Department of *Kaumarbhritya* for further needful management. The patient has persistent history of eadache for 1 year. For this the patient had taken treatment for a nearby private clinic and was under medication for 1 month, the patient felt relief during the medication period. Then, after the discontinuation of the medication, there was recurrence of the same complaints.

Personal history

Appetite	Normal
Thirst	Normal
Diet	Mixed
Micturition	Regular
Bowel	Regular
Sleep	Disturbed

Ashtavidha Pariksha

<i>Nadi</i>	<i>Kapha vataj</i>
<i>Mal</i>	<i>Prakrit</i>
<i>Mutra</i>	<i>Prakrit</i>
<i>Jihva</i>	<i>Malavrit</i>
<i>Shabad</i>	<i>Samanya</i>
<i>Sparsh</i>	<i>Samanya</i>
<i>Drik</i>	<i>Samanya</i>
<i>Akriti</i>	<i>Samanya</i>

Dashavidha Pariksha

<i>Prakriti</i>	<i>Kapha Pitta</i>
<i>Vikriti</i>	<i>Kapha Vata</i>
<i>Satva</i>	<i>Madhyama</i>
<i>Satmya</i>	<i>Madura, Amla, Lavana</i>
<i>Ahara Shakti</i>	<i>Madhyama</i>
<i>Vyayama Shakti</i>	<i>Madhyama</i>
<i>Sara</i>	<i>Mansa, Asthi</i>
<i>Samhanana</i>	<i>Madhyama</i>
<i>Agni Shakti</i>	<i>Madhyama</i>
<i>Vaya</i>	<i>Balyavastha</i>

General Examination

General condition	Good
Temperature	Afebrile
Pulse rate	80 bpm
Respiratory rate	20/min
Pallor	-ve
Icterus	-ve
Lymphadenopathy	-ve
Cyanosis\ clubbing	-ve
Oedema	-ve
Dehydration	-ve

Systemic Examination**Gastrointestinal System**

Inspection : shape of abdomen - Scaphoid

Umbilicus -normal, inverted

Palpation : Soft, no tenderness, no organomegaly

Percussion : Tympanic sounds heard except the area of liver dullness

Auscultation : Bowel Sound - Present

Central Nervous System

Patient is conscious, well oriented to time, place and person.

Respiratory System

Inspection: Shape of chest -bilaterally symmetrical

Palpation: Trachea - centrally placed

Tactile vocal fremitus - Normal

Percussion: Resonant sounds heard except the cardiac dullness

Auscultation: Normal vesicular breath sounds heard

Cardiovascular System

Inspection: No scar, no swelling

Palpation: Non tender

Percussion: Defined area of cardiac dullness

Auscultation: Apex beat felt at 5th intercostal space S1 and S2 heard, No added sounds or murmurs heard.

Final diagnosis: *Ardhvbhedak (Migraine)*

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Method

Center of study: RGGPG AYURVEDIC COLLEGE AND HOSPITAL, PAPROLA

Study Design: Single case study.

Criteria for Assessment^[7]

Subjective criteria

1. Headache (severity)
2. Headache (Duration)
3. Nausea

4. Vomiting
5. Photophobia
6. Episodes of attack
7. Aura
8. Other symptoms like Giddiness, Lack of sleep, Weakness, Fatigue.

Severity of Headache	0 - Absent 1 - Pain tolerable 2 - Disturbing Routine work 3 - Intolerable pain
Duration of Headache	0 - Nil 1 - 2-6hr /day 2 - 6-12hr/day 3 - \geq 12 hr/day
Nausea	0-None 1 - Loss of appetite without alterations in eating habits 2 - Oral intake decreased without significant weight loss, dehydration or malnutrition. 3 - Inadequate oral fluid intake, tube feeding, TPN or hospitalization indicated.
Vomiting	0 - None 1 - 1 to 2 episodes in 24 hours 2 - 3-5 episodes in 24 hours 3 - \geq 6 episodes in 24 hours
Photophobia	0 - No sensitive to light 1 - Mild sensitive to light but can tolerate with work 2 - Mild Sensitive to light but can't tolerate with work 3 - Can't tolerate light; needs either darkness or lights completely off
Episodes of attack	0 - No attacks within 1 month 1 - 1-3 attacks in 1 month 2 - 4-6 attacks in 1 month 3 - \geq 6 attacks in 1 month
Aura	0 - Nil 1 - Lasts for 5-10minutes 2 - Lasts for 10-15 minutes 3 - Lasts for >15 minutes
Other symptoms like Giddiness Lack of sleep Weakness Fatigue	0 - None 1 - Mild 2 - Moderate

Material**Panchkarma therapy**

- *Shirodhara* with *Dashmoola kwath*
- *Nasya* with *Brahmi Ghrit*.
- *Akshitarpan* with *Brahmi Ghrit*.

Shamanaushadhi : *Shirshooladi Vajra Rasa, Trikatu Churan*

Therapeutic Intervention

Date	Symptoms	Treatment
02/01/2024 (15 days)	Severe throbbing pain in left half of head and periorbital region along with nausea.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>Shirshooladi Vajra Rasa</i> 500 mg BD. 2. <i>Trikatu Churan</i> 3gm BD B/F. 3. <i>Nasya</i> with <i>Brahmi Ghrita</i> 4 drops in each nostril. 4. <i>Shirodhara</i> with <i>Dashmoola Kwath</i>. 5. <i>Akshitarpan</i> with <i>Brahmi Ghrita OD</i>.
04/02/2024 (15 days)	45% <i>Upashaya</i> There was marked reduction in pain in periorbital region and left side of head along with moderate relief in nausea.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>Shirshooladi Vajra Rasa</i> 500 mg BD. 2. <i>Trikatu Churan</i> 3gm BD B/F. 3. <i>Nasya</i> with <i>Brahmi Ghrita</i> 4 drops in each nostril. 4. <i>Shirodhara</i> with <i>Dashmoola Kwath</i>. 5. <i>Akshitarpan</i> with <i>Brahmi Ghrita OD</i>.
05/03/2024 (15 days)	80% <i>Upashaya</i> Occasional pain persisted in Lt. side of head whereas complete relief was observed in periorbital pain and nausea .	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>Shirshooladi Vajra Rasa</i> 500 mg BD. 2. <i>Trikatu Churan</i> 3gm BD B/F. 3. <i>Nasya</i> with <i>Brahmi Ghrita</i> 4 drops in each nostril. 4. <i>Shirodhara</i> with <i>Dashmoola Kwath</i>.
08/04/2024	Relief in all symptoms.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>Nasya</i> with <i>Brahmi Ghrita</i> 4 drops in each nostril. 2. <i>Shirodhara</i> with <i>Dashmoola Kwath</i>.

RESULT

Sign /symptoms	BT	1 st sitting	2 nd sitting	3 rd sitting	4 th sitting	AT
Headache (severity of pain)	3	Nasya with <i>Brahmi ghrita</i> followed by <i>Akshitarpan</i> and <i>Shirodhara</i> along with internal medications for 15 days.	Nasya with <i>Brahmi ghrita</i> followed by <i>Akshitarpan</i> and <i>Shirodhara</i> along with internal medications for 15 days	Nasya with <i>Brahmi ghrita</i> followed by <i>Shirodhara</i> along with internal medications for 15 days.	Nasya with <i>Brahmi ghrita</i> followed by <i>Shirodhara</i> for 15 days.	0
Headache (Duration of pain)	3					0
Nausea	3					0
Vomiting	1					0
Photophobia	1					1
Episodes of attack	3					0
Aura	3					0
Other symptoms like vertigo, lack of sleep, weakness, fatigue	3					1

DISCUSSION

In migraine, ayurvedic principles have shown convenient, safe and least expensive in comparison to the conventional method of treatment. *Shodhana* (purification) and *Shamana* (pacifying) therapy are two limbs of Ayurveda treatment. Migraine being correlated to *Ardhavabhedaka*, *Shodhana* procedures *Nasya* and *Virechana*, and *Shamana* medicines in the form of medicated ghee and polyherbal decoctions have been vividly prescribed as effective interventions in the classicherein the drugs, dietary and lifestyle modifications were chosen on

the basis of *Nidana* (causative factors of disease, involvement of dominant *Doshas* (*Vata-Kapha*) and Nature of *vyadhi* (disease).

Shirodhara

Shirodhara is an Ayurvedic *Panchkarma* therapy described by *Vagbhata* in *Ashtang Hridaya*. It also described in other books of *Panchkarma*.^[8] The etymology of the word *Shirodhara* is from *Shira* = Head and *Dhara* = steady flow. In *Shirodhara*, medicated oil, milk, buttermilk or *kwatha* are poured over the forehead of the patient in the form of regular stream from a height of precisely 3.14 inches as mentioned in *Dharakalpa* of *Sahastrayoga* and with a fixed oscillated movement.

In *Ayurveda*, Migraine is said to be an affliction of *Vata dosha*. This Ayurvedic therapy corrects this *dosha's* imbalance and gives permanent relief from migraine, as *Shirodhara* does. Adequate blood supply has been proven to be of paramount importance in supporting various functions of the human brain. *Shirodhara* aids in increasing the flow of blood to your head; therefore, the brain gets an adequate supply of oxygen and nutrients. This can assist one in preventing those sorely painful episodes of migraine.

Nasya therapy

It is an Ayurvedic *Panchkarma* therapy that involves administration of herbal medicine by the route of nasal cavity. It purifies and opens head's pathways which enhances Prana's oxygenation process and positively affects how the brain functions. On administration, the potency of the herbs used for nasal instillation reach *Shringataka* (the vital point at the base of the nose), and then the potency spreads to the head, eyes, ear, and throat, and aids in expelling the morbid *Doshas* (*vitiated humour*) from the head.^[9]

Mode of action of Go-Ghrita Nasya

- *Ghrita* is regarded as the best among *Jangama Sneha* and is known for and is *Balavardhaka, Ojovardhaka, Vayasthapana, Agni Deepana* and *Dhatuposhaka* properties. By virtue of its *Sanskaranuvartana* property, it attains the properties of ingredients without losing its own. According to *Acharya Charaka*, *Ghrita* is effective in subsiding *Pittaja* and *Vataja* disorders; it improves *Dhatu*s and is overall booster for improving *Ojas*. *Ghrita* having *Balya, Brimhana, Rasayana* and *Medhya* effect which can be explained by two ways. Digestion, absorption and delivery to the target organ are made easy when any drug is processed with *Ghrita* due to its lipophilic action. Anti-oxidant effect of *Go-Ghrita* is due to

its Vitamin A and Vitamin E content. According to *Acharaya Sushruta* in *ardhavbhedak* use *Goghrita Nasya*,^[10] and *Acharya Dalhanacharya* explain that *GoGhrita Nasya* is effective in *vataj Pittaj Avastha*.^[11] *Shiro Shuddhi* by *Nasya* removes the *Srotorodha* and opens the channels to receive the *Sneha*. Also, *Nasya Karma* is a specific treatment methodology mainly indicated for *Urdhvajatrugata Vikaras* in *Ayurveda*. Before *Nasya*, *Abhyanga* is specifically done in *Murdha Pradesha* which causes vasodilatation in the skin and muscles by stimulating receptors of the sympathetic nervous system. Vasodilatation increases blood flow and helps to remove the toxic products.

- *Acharya Charaka* has described the mechanism of *Swedana Karma* as it helps to dissolve *Shleshma*, makes the channels soft, by which *Vatadi Doshas* and other contents can flow through in their normal directions, and increases the secretion of vitiated *Shleshma* through the channel. So, due to *Ushna Guna* of *Swedana*, *Kapha Dosh* gets liquefied.^[12] *Brahmi Ghrita Nasya* reaches the cranial channels and pacifies aggravated *Vata*, the main cause of *Ardhavbhedaka*. Its cooling and *Medhya* properties calm nerve irritation, reduce *Pitta*-related inflammation, and relieve throbbing pain. By clearing *Kapha* blockage in the head through *Srotoshodhana*, it improves circulation and helps reduce both the intensity and frequency of headaches.

Akshitarpana

The *Ghrita* has the quality of trespassing into minute channels of the body. Hence, when applied in the eye, it enters deeper layers of *Dhatu*s and cleanses every minute part of them. Therapeutic efficacy of *Akshi Tarpana* can be understood through a multidimensional mode of action by *Tridosha Samana* (Dosha Balancing Mechanism), *Srotoshodhana* and *Snehana* (Channel Cleansing and Lubrication), *Dhatu Poshana* (Tissue Nourishment), *Indriya Prasadana* (Sensory Rejuvenation), *Agni* and *Vyana* Regulation (Metabolic and Circulatory Effects).^[13] *Akshi Tarpana* with *Brahmi Ghrita* nourishes the ocular tissues and calms the *Urdhvajatrugata Vata*, which is the primary factor in *Ardhavbhedaka*. Since the eyes and the head share common neural and vascular pathways (*Shringataka Marma*), the sustained contact of medicated *Ghrita* around the eyes helps stabilize nerve impulses and reduce *Vata*-induced spasmodic pain. *Brahmi*'s cooling and *Medhya* actions soothe *Pitta* irritation, reduce photophobia, and minimize stress-related triggers that aggravate migraine.

The unctuous, penetrating property of *Ghrita* enhances nourishment of ocular–cranial channels, reduces dryness, and decreases nerve sensitivity. By clearing subtle *Kapha*

obstructions and supporting smooth functioning of *Vata*, *Akshi Tarpana* with *Brahmi Ghrita* helps reduce headache intensity, improves eye comfort, and provides a calming, grounding effect to the entire head region.

Shamanaushadhi

The herbo-mineral combination known as *Shirashooladi Vajra Rasa* was also used in this case which possesses strong *Kapha–Vata–shamana* properties. Its formulation includes ingredients that not only pacify *Vata* and *Kapha* but also strengthen the nerves (*Nadi Balya*). Owing to its *Sukshma* and *Teekshna* qualities, the medicine can penetrate even the finest *Srotas*, promoting effective cleansing. Its *Laghu* and *Ruksha* attributes help remove *Avarana*, while the predominantly *Shothahara* and *Shoolahara* actions work to reduce inflammation and relieve the headache, which is the primary symptom addressed in this study.

CONCLUSION

This case study shows that an Ayurvedic treatment approach combining *Nasya*, *Shirodhara*, *Akshi Tarpana*, and *Shamana* medicines like *Brahmi Ghrita* and *Shirashooladi Vajra Rasa* along with *Trikatu Churan* can effectively reduce the intensity and frequency of migraine (*Ardhavabhedaka*). By pacifying *Vata–Kapha*, clearing *Srotorodha*, and nourishing the cranial channels, the therapy provided significant relief from headache and associated symptoms. These results suggest that *Ayurveda* offers a safe, holistic, and cost-effective option for managing migraine, warranting further clinical exploration.

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